

AI-Based Energy Demand Forecasting for a Smart Farm

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ABSTRACT: Modern farming is facing more problems mainly because resources are not used properly, energy costs keep increasing every year, and tools that help farmers plan ahead are still not available in many situations. This has become a serious concern. Because of this, managing farms has become more difficult than before, especially when decisions are made without proper or timely information, which often results in unnecessary energy usage. To deal with this issue, this study talks about the development of a Smart Farm Energy Forecasting System that combines energy estimation with irrigation-related guidance in a single setup.

The proposed system uses commonly monitors environmental factors of the kind such as temperature, humidity, soil moisture, rainfall, and duration of sunlight. These factors are important in farming. Together, they affect how much energy is needed during different farming activities and under different field conditions. The collected data is processed using a hybrid XGBoost and LSTM model, which helps the system generate real-time estimates of energy demand at the farm level. The results change as the conditions change.

The platform is developed as a streamlit-based web application with support for role-based access. It is kept easy to use. Farmers can quickly check predicted energy requirements and also get basic suggestions that can be followed during regular farming work. Technical changes are made whenever needed to improve the accuracy of model.

To make the prediction results easier to understand, methods for explaining the model output are also included in the system. SHAP values are used for this purpose. Overall, the proposed system provides a simple and practical way to estimate energy demand in real time while considering environmental conditions, and helps farmers take better decisions in daily agricultural practices.

1. INTRODUCTION

Agriculture still one of the sectors which use lot of energy, because energy keeps increasing with modern machines, automated watering systems and tools for checking environment conditions. Even after all these improvements, many farms still follow old ways of deciding without any forecasting data. This cause unnecessary energy use, costs going high, and irrigation not always done properly.

As the environment keep changing through the day, farmers often find it very difficult to decide the right time and duration for irrigation, which most of the time ends up wasting water, energy, and other resources, and also reduces overall productivity of the farm. Sometimes, even experienced farmers cannot judge properly because weather and soil conditions keep shifting during the day. The rise of AI and machine learning give chance to fix these problems in a proper way using data-based energy and resource management. Instead of guessing, farmers can rely on predictions and suggestions from smart systems. The Smart Farm Energy Forecasting System try to predict energy demand at farm level accurately, using important environmental things like temperature, humidity, soil moisture, rainfall, and hours of sunlight. By looking at all these factors together, it can understand patterns that humans may miss.

The system use a Hybrid LSTM-XGBoost model, where LSTM finds time-based patterns or trends in the environmental data over days or weeks, and XGBoost improve prediction accuracy using gradient-boosted decision trees. This combined method give better results than using only one model, and it works even in different weather or climate conditions, like rainy season or hot summer days. It can handle sudden changes too, so farmers don't have to worry about unexpected energy use.

To make things more clear and easy to understand, the system include an Explainable AI (XAI) part which use SHAP values to show how each factor affect energy demand. This help farmers know why the system predict like that, instead of just showing numbers. Also, there is a Smart Scheduling module which automatically find the best time for irrigation, usually early morning or late evening, by matching irrigation with time of low energy use. This not only reduce energy costs but also save water and make daily farm planning efficient.

2. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The Smart Farm Energy Forecasting System use a modular, data-focused structure with four main layers: Data Acquisition, Hybrid Prediction Engine, Application Interface, and Decision Intelligence Layer. The design make sure data flows smoothly from sensors to AI-based energy predictions, irrigation suggestions, and easy-to-understand insights.

A. Data Acquisition Layer

This layer gather and organize environmental factors needed for prediction. Users can give data in two ways:

(i) Dataset Upload: The system process datasets that include the temperature, humidity, soil moisture, rainfall, and sunlight duration.

(ii) Manual Entry: Streamlit UI let users enter current environmental data. All input data is cleaned, checked, and stored temporarily for forecasting and showing results.

B. Combined Prediction Engine (LSTM + XGBoost)

The prediction backend use a hybrid learning framework, which have the following components.

(i) XGBoost Regression Module: It is trained using structured data collected from the agricultural sensors.

It records nonlinear relationships between different environmental factors. The model is stored as `xgb_model.joblib` for quick use in the application.

(ii) LSTM Time-Series Component: It analyze past energy usage in a sequential way.

It learn temporal patterns using a 24-step sequence window. Normally with MinMax scaling and stored as `lstm_model.h5`.

(iii) Hybrid Fusion Mechanism: The final hybrid prediction is calculated as a weighted sum:

$$Hybrid = 0.55 \times LSTM + 0.45 \times XGBoost$$

It make sure the system is strong by combining feature-based learning (XGBoost) with trend-based learning (LSTM).

The hybrid results are saved in `predictions.csv` for checking and analysis.

Fig 1: illustrates the modular architecture of the Smart Farm Energy Forecasting System.

C. Application Interface Layer

In `app.py`, this layer give an interactive user interface for:

Data Submission: Upload documents or enter data by hand.

Prediction Output: Get instant energy usage estimate using the uploaded model.

Dashboard: Show trends with Plotly, including:

- History of energy demand
- Averages of different variables
- Recent forecast records

All user inputs and predicted energy values are saved as `predictions_with_schedule.csv` for continuous monitoring.

D. Decision Intelligence Layer

(i) Explainable AI Module (XAI): SHAP is used to help understand XGBoost predictions. Visual explanations show the importance of each environmental factor. In the app interface, simple rule-based notes make SHAP insights easier to follow.

(ii) Irrigation Suggestion System: It usages temperature, humidity, and soil moisture readings to decide irrigation method: Drip, Sprinkler, or Manual. The rules are based of usual farming practices.

(iii) Intelligent Scheduling System: It suggest best time and duration for irrigation according to predicted energy levels. The schedules are saved automatically in `latest_schedule.joblib`. This make sure irrigation happens when energy demand is low, saving energy and improving efficiency.

3. METHODOLOGY

The system use a hybrid predictive model with two stages to improve accuracy of energy-demand forecasting in smart farming.

Stage 1 - LSTM: The Long Short-Term Memory network find temporal patterns from sequential sensor data like temperature, humidity, soil moisture, sunlight, and past energy use. LSTM give feature outputs that capture long-term relationships in the data.

Stage 2 - XGBoost: The features from LSTM are given to an XGBoost regressor, which handle nonlinear relationships and reduce prediction errors using gradient boosting. XGBoost improve the final prediction by combining decision trees with the features learned by LSTM. This way, LSTM is used for time-series patterns and XGBoost is more accurate regression, giving better results than using only one model per detection.

B. Model Training and Evaluation

Data Preparation: Raw IoT sensor data is cleaned and converted into time-windowed sequences ready for LSTM input. Missing values are filled using interpolation or forward-fill.

Training Process: LSTM is trained first in a sequence-to-one setup. The output from LSTM's final hidden layer is saved as a feature vector. These vectors are then given to XGBoost for supervised regression training.

Evaluation Metrics: The system is tested using RMSE, MAE, and R² score. Train-test split or k-fold validation is used to check performance properly. Results are compared with baseline models (only LSTM, only XGBoost) to show that the hybrid model works better.

C. Explainable AI (XAI) Integration

To make the model more reliable, this system use the XAI framework.

SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations): It is used to find how much each feature contribute to the final energy-demand forecast, like how temperature affect it or how solar radiation affect it.

D. Smart Irrigation Recommendation Module

The prediction results are used to improve irrigation scheduling. The hybrid model predict future energy needs and water usage using environmental data.

A threshold-based or rule-based engine then:

- Suggests best irrigation schedules to save energy costs.
- Helps avoid collision during high-demand times.
- Recommends water allocation based on soil moisture and weather forecasts.

This module make sure energy is used efficiently and water is saved during irrigation, helping with precision farming.

Fig 2: Depicts the methodology of the Smart Farm Energy Forecasting System

4. DATA AND PROCESSING

The Smart farm energy forecasting system use a mix of IoT sensor data and generated time-based features to make more accurate energy consumption predictions.

(i) Data Sources: The dataset include different environmental and operational factors:

1. Temperature (°C): Shows environmental conditions which affecting irrigation and energy use.
2. Humidity (%): Shows moisture in the air which will affect soil evaporation.
3. Soil Moisture (%): Shows water level in soil, so much important for deciding irrigation.
4. Precipitation (mm): Natural water supply for crops.
5. Sunlight Duration: Helps check crop water loss and energy needed for lights or pumps.
6. Temporal Characteristics: Hour of day, day of year, and weekday are taken for to reflect daily and seasonal energy levels.

Data is collected either from dataset files like CSV uploads or manual entry through the Streamlit interface, allowing both historical analysis and real-time forecasting.

(ii) **Data Preparation:** This step makes the input data is clean and uniform for the hybrid model.

Data Cleaning: Missing data is handled using interpolation or by forward-fill methods.

Normalization: Continuous variables are scaled using MinMax normalization so that in turn LSTM can train properly.

Sequence Generation: For LSTM, data is arranged in fixed-length time windows to capture temporal relationships.

Feature Engineering: Environmental and time-based features are combined to form the full input matrix for both XGBoost and LSTM.

(iii) **Data Storage and Management:** All processed data, forecasts, and schedule results are saved in CSV files (predictions_with_schedule.csv) or Joblib files (latest_schedule.joblib). This allow easy access for dashboard display, smart irrigation scheduling, and XAI evaluation.

(iv) **Summary of Workflow:**

Unprocessed sensor data is first collected and checked. Preprocessing convert data into sequences for LSTM and feature sets for XGBoost. The hybrid LSTM–XGBoost model then forecast energy demand. These forecasts are used by the smart irrigation system to give practical suggestions for water allocation and saving energy.

5. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

This part discuss about the working results of the proposed AI-driven Smart Farm Energy Forecasting System. The results show how well the system can forecast energy, how data is represented, and how smart suggestions work. It also look at the patterns noticed and points out the limits of the current implementation.

A. System Functionality and Workflow

The system is launched through streamlit interface that let users input data manually or upload datasets, making it flexible for different users. After entering environmental things like temperature, humidity, soil moisture, rainfall, and sunlight hours, the system also create time based features like hour, weekday, and day of year. It automatically decide the irrigation type before giving the final energy forecast.

All forecasts are saved in a constantly updating database, so users can track things over time. The platform also have a dashboard that show past predictions, calculate basic statistics, and display the latest entries. This way, prediction, visualization, and storage work smoothly without needing extra setup from the user limits of the current implementation.

B. Predicted Energy Trend Analysis

The line graph showing Predicted Energy Over Time, show how energy demand change over time based on past predictions. The graph also show short-term changes caused by changing environmental factors.

Periods with high temperature and long sunlight usually have higher predicted energy demand. When it is cooler or more humid, energy use goes down. This show that the model can catch patterns in energy use based on environment. The time-series trends also help farmers see repeated peak-demand periods and plan machinery use during off-peak times.

Figure 3: Predicted Energy Over Time. This line graph illustrates the temporal variation in predicted energy demand based on historical environmental inputs.

C. Environmental Variable Analysis

The bar graph for Average of Key Environmental Variables show the mean values of all important factors along with the average predicted energy. This graph help to understand the general environmental conditions where the model was working. Some important things noticed are:

- Higher average soil moisture and humidity usually match with moderate predicted energy.
- The average predicted energy in the dataset stays in a manageable range, showing that most of the recorded cycles had stable environmental conditions.

This collected data help to check the quality of the dataset and also help in better irrigation scheduling and managing resources.

Figure 4: Average of Key Environmental Variables. This bar chart presents the mean values of major environmental parameters alongside the average predicted energy.

D. Performance of AI-Based Prediction Model

The XGBoost model, which use environmental and time-based features, showed really good prediction performance with low MAE and RMSE in the validation. This prove that tree-based boosting methods work well for non-linear, sensor-based agricultural data.

The system also include LSTM for time-based modeling in the backend, which allow hybrid analysis. Right now, the live system use only XGBoost for the user interface, but the hybrid model (XGBoost + LSTM) give smoother predictions over time. This show that sequential learning is important for energy forecasting.

```

Sample Hybrid Predictions:
timestamp  hybrid_pred
115 2024-01-31 00:00:00 15.041843
460 2024-02-01 00:00:00 15.268581
400 2024-02-01 00:00:00 14.531134
178 2024-02-01 00:00:00 15.123105
11 2024-02-02 00:00:00 14.400856
256 2024-02-02 00:00:00 15.303722
66 2024-02-03 00:00:00 15.511118
356 2024-02-04 00:00:00 14.578922
14 2024-02-05 00:00:00 15.274811
357 2024-02-06 00:00:00 14.531103

```

Figure 5: Prediction Results in Terminal

E. Explainable AI and Smart Scheduling

The Explainable AI module give rule-based irrigation advice and hence decide the best irrigation type (drip, sprinkler, or manual) based on combined soil moisture and humidity levels. The system also automatically create watering times and operation schedules, helping users shift high-energy tasks to off-peak hours.

This combination make sure predictions are not only accurate but also give useful decision support, making the system practical for real farming optimization.

Figure 6: Illustrates how the Explainable AI module interprets moisture-humidity conditions to recommend the irrigation type and schedule.

The image show sprinkler irrigation, decided by the rule-based scheduler. It pick the irrigation type based on the data given to the model.

Figure 7: Smart Farm XAI based Recommendations Results

The illustration show the recommendations given by the smart farm system using Explainable AI. It show how the system look at important sensor data like soil moisture, humidity, temperature, and available energy to make clear, rule-based suggestions.

The image shows a table titled "Smart Scheduling Recommendations" with a clock icon. The table has five columns: ID, Time of Day (hr:min:sec), Predicted Energy (kWh), Recommended Watering Duration, and Temperature (°C). The data is as follows:

ID	Time of Day (hr:min:sec)	Predicted Energy (kWh)	Recommended Watering Duration	Temperature (°C)
136	18:30:00	13.5	15 minutes	30
137	19:30:00	15.2	10 minutes	10
138	18:30:00	14.43	15 minutes	50
139	18:30:00	13.5	15 minutes	30
140	18:30:00	13.5	15 minutes	30
141	18:30:00	13.5	15 minutes	30
142	18:30:00	13.5	15 minutes	30
143	18:30:00	13.5	15 minutes	30
144	18:30:00	13.5	15 minutes	30
145	18:30:00	13.5	15 minutes	30

Figure 8: Smart Scheduling Recommendations Results

The diagram depicts the intelligent scheduling suggestions produced by the system, indicating how forecasted energy needs and environmental factors are utilized to identify the best time periods for running agricultural machinery

F. Discussion and Limitations

The results show that the system can predict energy demand properly and also give useful farm suggestions. But there are some limitations:

Dataset Constraints: The model performance depend on the quality and variety of the dataset available. Bigger and more seasonally diverse data would help it work better in general.

Static Rule-Based Logic: The irrigation suggestion system still follow fixed thresholds. Using reinforcement learning or dynamic optimization could make it more flexible in complex farm situations.

Local Storage Dependency: Prediction history and schedules are saved locally, which limit scalability. For multiple farms, cloud or distributed storage would be needed.

Limited Real-Time Integration: Right now, the system need manual input or CSV data. Connecting IoT sensors in real-time is a future improvement to allow continuous and automatic forecasting.

6. CONCLUSION

This study introduce a smart energy-demand prediction system for intelligent farming using a hybrid LSTM-XGBoost model with Explainable AI and advanced scheduling. The system can catch time-based trends from environmental and operational data, giving accurate short-term energy forecasts that are important for modern farm automation.

Using XAI make the model’s decisions easier to understand, so farmers can see which factors affect the predictions most. The smart scheduling module turn these insights into practical suggestions, improving irrigation timing, equipment use, and overall energy consumption. This help save energy, reduce costs, and manage resources better in real farming.

In short, the system show how AI-based predictions, clear insights, and automation can together improve sustainable farming. Future work can be improved by making this system by adding real time renewable energy, handling multiple crops, and self-learning features for a more resilient farm operations.

7. FUTURE WORK

Future improvements of this system can make it even more efficient, scalable, and useful in smart farming. One main focus is adding the active sensor networks that give real-time info about on moisture, humidity, temperature, and energy use. This will let the forecasting model work dynamically and respond better to sudden changes in environment.

Using more advanced hybrid deep learning frameworks, like that of CNN-LSTM, attention-based LSTM, or transformer models for time-series, can improve prediction accuracy by catching long-range patterns and complex feature interactions. Expanding the platform to use cloud storage and computing will allow handling big datasets, enable remote monitoring, and support multiple farms without hardware problems. Extra improvements to Explainable AI will make predictions easier for farmers to understand, clearly showing how each environmental factor affect energy use and irrigation planning. Also, adding adaptive irrigation optimization that change water flow and schedules according to crop type, soil type, and energy availability can make the system more independent and efficient.

In short, these future updates can turn the system from just a prediction tool into a fully autonomous, self-optimizing smart farm platform that help save money, improve sustainability, and support big farming operations.

8. REFERENCES

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